

CHRONIC BRONCHITIS – MANAGEMENT ACCORDING TO DIFFERENT SYSTEM OF MEDICINE: A REVIEW

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Abstract

Introduction: Chronic bronchitis is one of the conditions that is treated the most frequently, it is also one of the most ignored. It is necessary to review published papers and other studies on the management of chronic bronchitis with different medical systems because they will offer a thorough overview of the management of chronic bronchitis according to various medical systems, emphasising the advantages of each approach and the significance of individualised treatment plans. Different systems show different aspects of different systems with regard to the causes of chronic bronchitis and their expected outcomes, depending on different treatment techniques.

Methodology - Several articles were retrieved from internet sources such as PubMed, Medline, Scopus, and others. A thorough examination of several sorts of articles on the management of chronic bronchitis in various medical systems like Allopathy, Ayurveda, Yoga, Unani, and Homoeopathy was conducted.

Results: A total of 5603 articles were analyzed, and 21 publications were chosen for examination based on inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Conclusion: The study concludes that Chronic Bronchitis is the leading cause of suffering in patients and one of the leading causes of fatalities worldwide; thus, different systems are studied together to highlight the different approaches of different systems. The study emphasizes on effectiveness of different medications, herbal formulations, dietary modifications, and lifestyle changes in managing chronic bronchitis. It also highlights the importance of preventing acute exacerbations and strengthening the immune system. It aims to provide insights into the different treatment options available for chronic bronchitis and their potential benefits though more research is required for a holistic approach to management.

Keyword: Chronic Bronchitis, chronic cough, Allopathy, Ayurveda, Unani, Homoeopathy, Yoga and Hyper mucus Secretion.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Chronic Bronchitis CB is characterized as chronic cough and sputum production over 3 months per year for 2 consecutive years. Other classifications include chronic phlegm production, chronic cough with sputum production, and chronic hypersecretion of the bronchi. There are many definitions of chronic bronchitis abbreviated as CB and chronic mucus hypersecretion abbreviated as CMH¹ that have been developed over the years. However, the fundamental element of each definition is the excessive mucus production from hyperplasia of submucosal glands in large airways like the trachea and bronchi, without any known cause.

1.2 Epidemiology

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is the third leading cause of death worldwide, causing 3.23 million deaths in 2019. Nearly 90% of COPD deaths in those under 70 years of age occur in low- and middle-income countries (LMIC). Prevalence of Chronic Bronchitis in India is 5.0%². Initially, it was considered to be a diseases of elderly people above 40 but now after numerous studies³. It has been seen in several studies that it can occur even at early adult age like 18+ years.

Both genders are equally prone to have CB but according to this study⁴ females are more prone to severe morbidities as compared to males.

1.3 Etiology

Smoking is the most typical cause of chronic bronchitis, and although other irritants, including dust, fumes, and air pollution which can also contribute to the condition causation and exacerbation. Some studies suggested, genetic factors might also be important ⁵.

1.4 Pathophysiology

The pathophysiology of CB is chronic airway inflammation due to recurrent environmental factors and sometimes genetic factors leading to overproduction and Hypersecretion of mucus along with impaired mucociliary clearance ^{1,2,6}.

1.5 Clinical presentation

Patients with CB describe having a chronic cough, producing mucus, and/or having shortness of breath as symptoms. The presence of CB is linked to more severe and frequent exacerbations, decreased quality of life, and higher rates of morbidity and mortality.

Assessment – In most of the cases of CB, assessment was done on assessment scales and by physician's observation and diagnosis based on clinical presentations ^{1,6,7}.

1.6 Management –

There are different systems of medicines which are used worldwide and different systems have different mode of management and for chronic bronchitis different systems have different concepts for its management. Out of numerous studies, few studies which are selected on the bases of inclusion and exclusion criteria are presented below-

Tabular representation –

Sr. No.	Reference No.	Mode of treatment	Study type	Population	Intervention	Outcome Measures	Conclusion
1.	⁸	Instrumental intervention	Clinical trial	Adult patients with CB who were at least 40 years old and had smoked for at least 10 pack years made up the study population.	Bronchial Rheop	SGRQ scale was selected and the 4-points thresholds for CAT were used to assess the outcome	bronchial rheoplasty which is a new technique can be used to manage CB and to reduce the chances of acute exacerbation
2.	⁹	Allopathy	RCT	100 patients were enrolled and divided in 2 groups of 50-50 as placebo group and as Nacetylcysteine group	Oral N-acetylcysteine (NAC)	St. George's Respiratory Questionnaire (SGQR) and CBSAS scale.	Oral N-acetylcysteine (NAC) are frequently used and its efficacy is tested
3.	¹⁰	Allopathy	Meta – analysis	Different publications were searched upto year 2011	Different group of Antibiotics		Antibiotic prophylaxis significantly decreased the frequency of exacerbations in CB patients, although it is not recommended to use them long-term because resistance may develop.
4.	¹¹	Allopathy	Review article	Different RCTs were studied from different articles upto year 2019	Mucolytic agents		Antibiotic prophylaxis significantly decreased the frequency of exacerbations in CB patients, although it is not recommended to use them long-term because resistance may develop.
5.	¹²	Allopathy	Review article	Different RCTs and review	Broad spectrum of Antibiotics		This study concludes that Antibiotics are helpful during acute

				articles were studied			exacerbation and its helped in preventing hospitalization. It also stated that long term use of antibiotics should be avoided.
6.	¹³	Ayurveda	Research article	Patients of CB aged between 20 and 70 years	Bibhitakava leha	Subjective and objective assessment of patients was done	This formulation of bibhitakaval was found effective in management of CB and due to subjective and objective assessment of patients, which shows effectiveness of medicine as a whole.
7.	¹⁴	Ayurveda	Clinical Trial	Patients between 18 and 70 years who had CB were enrolled for research	Talisadi Churna (TC)	Primary outcome was measured with Leicester Cough Questionnaire (LCQ) score and secondary outcome was assessed by St. George's Respiratory Questionnaire (SGRQ) Score.	This study was helpful in management of chronic bronchitis using Talisadi Churna and the result of the present study also proves the safety of the TC as no ADR/AE were observed
8.	¹⁵	Ayurveda	Case study	57-year-old male patient with chronic bronchitis	Agastyaharitaki Avaleha; Vasa churna Dashmoola kwatha, Bharngi churna, and Sitopaladi Churna	Symptomatic analysis	This case study shows that combination of churnas can result in management of patients and can give relief to the patient.
9.	¹⁶	Ayurveda	Critical review		Nidana Parivarjana, different Shamnouthdhi and different modes of Shodana. Shamana drugs.	Symptomatic analysis	This review emphasizes of different modes of treatment at different stages to purify the body and manage the disease internally.

10.	¹⁷	Ayurveda	Clinical study	Patients which were enrolled aged between 16 to 70 years with History of uncompliated chronic bronchitis	Vyaghrihari taki Avaleha	St. George's Respiratory Questionnaire (SGRQ) scores	This study shows positive response in patients with
11.	¹⁸	Yoga	Clinical research	33 patients with COPD	Pranayama, kapalabhati, sithali		This study showed that six weeks of yoga, which included breathing exercises, asanas, pranayama, kalpalabhati, sithali exercises, and meditation, enhanced spirometric measurements, the RMS, and the Quality of life.
12.	¹⁹	Yoga	meta-analysis	This study has been the subject of 11 randomized trials for people with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.	Different techniques of yoga was analysed in different studies	COPD Assessment Test was used in most of the studies	This meta-analysis showed that different studies which were conducted at different sites for yoga efficacy were studied and overall it was concluded that yoga is safe to use and manage the cases of chronic bronchitis and copd
13.	²⁰	Yoga	Clinical research	Patients enrolled were of 18 years of age and older	Pranayama	primary outcome was a change in the 6-min walk distance (6MWD). While the Secondary outcomes was Dyspnea Scale score	This study successfully established a link between pranayama and increased exercise tolerance in COPD patients. Patients were successfully taught how to perform pranayama by lay staff.
14.	²¹	Yoga	meta-analysis	All the included participants were known case of COPD		The modified Jadad scale and St. George's Respiratory Questionnaire (SGRQ) scores	According to this meta-analysis, yoga training may be a suitable and appropriate adjunctive rehabilitation

							program for people with COPD..
15.	²²	Unani	Review article	Literature taken from different books	- Tanqiya (Purgation) - Ta'deel (Modulation) - Taskeen and – Taqweat (Different combination of drugs are used for management of chronic bronchitis)		There are different ways to deal with the disease as and under different ways there are different herbs which are used due to their particular property which is beneficial in management of chronic bronchitis
16.	²³	Unani	Case series	5 patients case study within age group of 35-65 years	Qurs and syrup was used. Qurs formulated from Filfil daraz, Kakra singhi, Jawa khaa, Aslusoos, Post Anaar and Adrak sabz.	CAT score	This study showed significant result in effective action of qurs formulation and its action on respiratory system.
17.	²⁴	Unani	Review		Literature stated different formulations of unani herbs which can be used.		This literature showed unani medicines, combinations, different modes to manage chronic bronchitis. It also stated the diet restriction and diet recommendation which can be given for management of cb along with unani medicines.
18.	²⁵	Homoeopathy	RCT	2 groups- control group and homoeopathic group consisting of patients between age group of 50-80 years	Oscillococinum was given and other group was given conventional medicine	CAT score	This study showed effective outcome of patients with CB and has shown decreased exacerbation of disease and superadded infection leading to better management of disease.

19.	²⁶	Homoeopathy	Review article		Different homoeopathic medicines according to different rubrics and few common homoeopathic medicines.		This article explained management of chronic bronchitis and with respect to homoeopathy rubrics related to chronic bronchitis and homoeopathic medicines used frequently are mentioned.
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2. Review of literature

For the review, the numerous electronic databases were searched, out of which few are: Medline, EMBASE, PubMed, Scopus, COCHRANE,, and Google Scholar. For searching different articles and different studies related to the topic, keywords for chronic bronchitis as, “Bronchitis,” “cough,” “COPD” were used. While for the search of different mode of treatment, Words used were, “Allopathy,” “Ayurveda”. “Homoeopathy”. “Yoga” and “Unani”. Numerous Clinical trials, Review articles, Observational studies, and In vitro studies were searched out and reviewed and as a result of the thorough search were collected.

Inclusion Criteria: the Research studies related to chronic bronchitis are particularly selected for the review where there is no acute exacerbation. Articles having main focus on management of CB are considered. Full article texts were studied and selected for the review. Total numbers of articles that were included in the study were 21.

Exclusion criteria: The Research articles having acute bronchitis were excluded from the study. Also, study which did not include any studies that encounters with bronchitis induced by drugs. Studies which do not have scale based diagnosis. Different journals were searched and are briefed in tabular form. As Table no. 2

3. Results:

A total of 5603 articles about chronic bronchitis were found in the review. Duplicate articles and those that didn't meet the criteria for inclusion were excluded from the study after screening. The review included a total of 21 studies. These included observational studies, randomized controlled trials, review articles, case study reviews, and meta-analyses. Details given in Table no. 1

4. DISSCUSSION –

- **Review of Allopathy** – Total of 5 studies were chosen for the study of various management in allopathy for chronic bronchitis, including clinical trials, RCTs, review articles, and meta-analyses. All of these studies generally demonstrated the need for antibiotic action for management and to

prevent super added infection ⁷, as well as the effectiveness of various mucolytic agents and the safety of rhinoplasty.

- **Review in Ayurveda** – a total of 5 studies was selected for review for management of chronic bronchitis according to Ayurvedic system. Different modes are there for management at different stages of chronic bronchitis like Nidana Parivarjana, shodhana and other modes which can be thought of for various stages of disease. As Ayurveda deals with internal healing and immunity boosting, therefore different combinations are used this gives anti-inflammatory results along with antibiotic and immune build up properties.
- **Review in yoga** – a total of 4 studies is included in reviews which are clinical trials and meta-analysis. These studies showed results of yoga in management of chronic bronchitis along with medication and which showed improvement in quality of life with help of different asanas like pranayama, shavaasan etc. yoga helped in improving exercise tolerance for CB patient. These studied overall showed effectiveness of yoga in management of CB.
- **Review in Unani** - Three studies in total—two reviews and one clinical trial—were included. As the Unani system of medicine relies on a combination of herbs and dietary modifications, many combinations are created to treat inflammation, relieve coughing, and thin mucus. All of these combinations are used in conjunction with dietary and lifestyle modifications to effectively manage CB.
- **Review of Homoeopathy** - Three studies altogether were included in the review. Homeopathic medicines are chosen based on symptom similarity since homoeopathy operates on the law of similia. Additionally, different medications are recommended based on various criteria and are chosen from several repertoires in accordance with symptoms. Since homoeopathy focuses on interior healing, it is impossible to specify how certain medications operate. A few often-utilized treatments are presented, which are more typically prescribed for the treatment of CB based on symptom similarities.

5. Conclusion

According to the aforementioned studies, different medical systems have varied approaches to treating chronic bronchitis, but every system works to stop bacterial infections that can cause acute exacerbations that require hospitalization. These trials also demonstrate that anti-inflammatory drugs are effective in treating chronic bronchitis, and strengthening the immune system will reduce the likelihood of disease recurrence. Because it is a chronic illness accompanied by bronchial inflammation, there is very little prospect of a full recovery; yet, managing such instances is crucial. As a result, numerous therapy modalities can be utilized singly or in combination to address the chronic bronchitis situation and though holistic further researches are required for benefit of mankind.

Conflict of Interest – None

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